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Making Retroduction Transparent: Integrating Danermark's Explanatory Protocol and the RRREIC Framework for Mechanism-Based Explanation in Critical Realist Qualitative Research

An Integrated Methodological Protocol with Worked Demonstration

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Keywords: Critical Realism · retroduction · methodological transparency · Danermark protocol · RRREIC · prospective instrument-framework alignment · generative mechanisms · qualitative research · mechanism-based explanation · methodological protocol

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Supplementary material

Ready-to-use blank templates (Tables 2, 3, 4, 5b, 9) and Appendices A–C (interview protocol, annotated coding excerpt, audit trail template) are provided as a separate supplementary file. Both files are uploaded together as part of the Zenodo preprint record.

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Abstract

Despite the growing influence of Critical Realism (CR) in organisational research, a persistent gap separates its philosophical commitments from its methodological practice: studies claiming a CR orientation routinely invoke retroduction and generative mechanisms without specifying how those concepts are implemented in data analysis. This limits the transparency, replicability, and theoretical contribution of CR-informed qualitative studies.

This article addresses this gap by introducing a practically operationalised, replicable analytical protocol for mechanism-based explanation in CR qualitative research. Drawing exclusively on the CR methodological literature and using constructed examples for demonstration purposes rather than empirical findings, the article provides a systematic guide for moving from research design to mechanism-based causal explanation. The guide integrates Danermark et al.'s (2002) seven-stage explanatory protocol with the RRREIC inferential framework and demonstrates how semi-structured interview instruments can be designed to generate the temporal, construct-specific evidence that retroductive inference requires. Post-acquisition integration serves as the demonstration domain solely because its structural conditions and generative mechanisms are sufficiently well-theorised in the existing literature to provide a clear analytical context; no empirical data were collected or analysed for this study.

The article makes three methodological contributions: (1) a replicable seven-stage protocol supported by five ready-to-use instruments that make every analytical decision auditable; (2) the novel principle of prospective instrument-framework alignment, which prevents post hoc mechanism labelling at the design stage; and (3) reconceptualisation of the Correction stage as the primary site for theoretical development through negative cases. All instruments and templates, including a complete interview protocol, annotated coding example, and audit trail, are provided in the online supplementary material. The protocol is intended for researchers seeking mechanism-based explanation in open systems where causal processes are not directly observable.

Keywords: Critical Realism, retroduction, methodological transparency, Danermark protocol, RRREIC, prospective instrument-framework alignment, generative mechanisms, qualitative research, mechanism-based explanation, methodological protocol

1. Introduction

This article uses post-acquisition integration (PAI) as a methodological demonstration domain — not as an empirical investigation of PAI itself. All examples of informant language, case configurations, and analytical outcomes presented in Section 5 are constructed to illustrate how the protocol operates at each stage; they do not represent actual informant accounts or empirical findings. No empirical data were collected or analysed for this study. The PAI domain was selected because its structural conditions (knowledge value and uniqueness) and generative mechanisms (barrier identity and proactivity) are sufficiently well-theorised in the existing literature to provide a clear and instructive demonstration context. Researchers applying the protocol in other domains will need to adapt the substantive construct definitions while retaining the analytical architecture.

In recent years, there has been an increasing interest in Critical Realism (CR) as a philosophical and analytical orientation for studying complex organisational processes. CR's appeal lies in its promise of causal depth: rather than describing what happens, CR-oriented studies seek to explain how and why outcomes are generated through the activation of generative mechanisms operating within specific structural and contextual configurations (Bhaskar, 1978; Danermark et al., 2002; Easton, 2010). However, much of the research published under a CR banner to date has been descriptive in nature. When CR researchers describe their analytical approach, references to retrodution and mechanism identification are common; specifications of how exactly retrodution was performed on the data remain rare. Fletcher (2017, p. 185), in a methodological review of CR qualitative studies, captures this problem directly: CR-informed studies frequently employ CR language without demonstrating CR logic, such that 'methodology meets method only rarely.' This observation is independently corroborated by Mingers and Standing (2017, p. 172), who find in their review of information systems research that 'the identification of mechanisms is asserted rather than demonstrated.' Together, these findings suggest that a methodological transparency problem exists with direct consequences for cumulative theory-building in organisational research.

The present study contributes to the CR methodological literature by integrating Danermark et al.'s (2002) explanatory sequence with the RRREIC inferential logic in a manner directly applicable to qualitative organisational research. Building on prior work in CR methodology, and to the best of the author's knowledge, no prior published account combines all five instruments — indicator tables with anti-confound guidance, inferential rules, a mapping matrix, an instrument-alignment template, and a Correction-stage worked example — within a single replicable framework.

The article makes three methodological contributions to Critical Realist qualitative research. First, it provides a practically operationalised seven-stage analytical protocol that integrates Danermark's explanatory sequence with the RRREIC inferential framework. The protocol is supported by five directly adaptable instruments, each designed to address a specific transparency failure identified in the CR methodological literature. Second, and arguably most consequentially, the article introduces prospective instrument-framework alignment as a design principle. Interview instruments are required to anticipate the inferential requirements of each protocol stage before data collection begins. This design feature structurally prevents the post hoc mechanism labelling that characterises much published CR-informed research. Third, the article reconceptualises the Correction stage as a primary site of theoretical development through negative cases. Disconfirming evidence thereby becomes a source of boundary-condition specification rather than an indication of model failure. The protocol is illustrated through a seven-case hypothetical demonstration in a knowledge-intensive acquisition context,

and all instruments are provided as ready-to-use templates in the online supplementary material.

The paper is structured as follows. Section 2 diagnoses the methodological gap. Section 3 introduces the component frameworks. Section 4 presents the full protocol with all instruments. Section 5 demonstrates the protocol across seven hypothetical cases. Section 6 addresses prospective instrument-framework alignment. Section 7 discusses contributions, compares the approach to existing methods, and addresses trustworthiness and limitations. Section 8 provides practical guidance for researchers. Section 9 concludes.

2. The Methodological Gap: Diagnosis and Organisational Research Consequences

2.1 Three Levels of CR Research and Where the Gap Occurs

Previous studies of CR methodology in organisational research have not dealt systematically with the question of how retroductive inference should be performed in practice. One criticism of much of the CR literature in organisational research is that it conflates philosophical positioning with methodological procedure. To appreciate the scope of this problem, it is useful to distinguish three levels at which CR-informed research must succeed: the philosophical (correctly invoking CR ontology), the conceptual (specifying appropriate structural conditions and mechanisms), and the analytical (systematically inferring mechanisms from data). A substantial body of published work succeeds at the first two levels while leaving the third — the analytical — underspecified (Fletcher, 2017; Mingers & Standing, 2017; Frederiksen & Kringelum, 2021).

A series of studies investigating the quality of CR-informed qualitative research has produced troubling findings. Fletcher's (2017) review of 34 CR qualitative studies finds that mechanism claims are made in 31 of them, but systematic retroductive inference procedures are described in fewer than five. Mingers and Standing (2017), reviewing 52 information systems studies, conclude that mechanisms are inferred post hoc from outcomes rather than from process evidence — a procedure that is logically circular and epistemically weak. Frederiksen and Kringelum (2021), in a systematic review of 26 CR-informed empirical studies in management and organisation, confirm this pattern: the majority of published CR studies constitute what they term 'peripheral' applications, in which critical realism is invoked as philosophical background rather than applied as a rigorous analytical procedure generating mechanism-based explanations. More recently, Danaeefard et al. (2025) identify methodological inconsistency as the field's primary constraint, suggesting that the analytical gap identified by Fletcher (2017) has persisted despite growing awareness of the problem. The pattern is systemic: the analytical gap is not the exception but the rule. This opacity not only impedes cumulative theory-building but also undermines CR's standing as a methodologically rigorous paradigm in mainstream management journals.

2.2 CR's Core Explanatory Logic and Why It Demands Systematic Procedure

It is now well established that Critical Realism posits a stratified ontology consisting of three interconnected domains: the real domain, containing structures and generative mechanisms with causal powers that exist independently of observation; the actual domain, comprising events that occur when mechanisms are activated; and the empirical domain, including those aspects of events that become observable by researchers (Bhaskar, 1978, 1979; Danermark et al., 2002). In open social systems, causation is contingent, context-dependent, and rarely

reducible to linear relationships between variables. Danermark (2019) formalises this logic as $S + M + C = O$ (Structure + Mechanism + Context = Outcome), a formula that maps directly onto the three-level explanatory architecture of the present protocol: structural conditions (S), generative mechanisms (M), and contextual enabling conditions (C) together produce observable integration outcomes (O).

The stratified ontology underpinning this formula has important methodological implications. Mukumbang (2021), in his work on retroductive theorising in mixed-methods research, notes that mechanisms themselves are stratified — operating at physical, biological, psychological, psychosocial, behavioural, social, cultural, and economic layers — and that mechanisms at a lower level can create conditions for the unfolding of mechanisms at a higher level, a capacity described as emergence (p. 95). This stratification explains why mechanism identification in organisational research cannot stop at behavioural description: the analyst must move from observable events at the empirical level to the causal structures operating at the level of the real.

Retroduction provides the principal inferential logic for CR explanation. Rather than asking whether variables are statistically associated, retroductive reasoning asks a fundamentally different question: ‘What underlying structures or mechanisms must exist for these observed events to be possible?’ This question distinguishes CR inquiry from conventional qualitative approaches. Adequate causal explanation in open systems is inherently contrastive: the question is not merely ‘why did X occur?’ but ‘why X rather than Y?’ (Lawson, 2003; Downward & Mearman, 2007). This contrastive standard has direct methodological consequences — mechanism claims that cannot answer the contrastive question remain descriptive rather than explanatory, which is precisely why the counterfactual test (Rule R2 in Section 4.2) is treated here as a necessary rather than optional inferential standard. Modell (2009), writing on the application of CR in management accounting research, observes that the validity of a causal explanation in CR is an attribute of the theory informing that explanation rather than a universally valid statement about the real world as such (p. 215). This position has direct implications for the inferential standards applied in Stage 4: mechanism claims must be evaluated against the theoretical framework generating them, not merely against the empirical outcomes they are intended to explain — which is precisely the circularity that Rule R4 is designed to prevent. A case-study approach was chosen here to allow a deeper insight into this inferential process, and qualitative methods offer an effective way of examining how the transition from empirical observation to mechanism-based explanation can be made systematic and transparent.

2.3 The Structure of This Article's Response

The following section introduces the two component frameworks — Danermark et al.’s (2002) explanatory protocol and the RRREIC inferential framework — and explains the generative logic of their integration. Section 4 then presents the full seven-stage protocol with all five operational instruments. Section 5 demonstrates the protocol through a methodological worked example. Section 6 develops the prospective instrument-framework alignment principle. Section 7 positions the protocol relative to existing CR and non-CR approaches, evaluates trustworthiness, and specifies boundary conditions. Section 8 provides practical implementation guidance, and Section 9 concludes.

3. The Component Frameworks and Their Integration

To date, various methods have been developed and introduced to support mechanism-based explanation in qualitative organisational research. Two of the most influential contributions

addressing this challenge are Danermark et al.'s (2002) explanatory protocol and the RRREIC inferential framework. Although both share a commitment to mechanism-based explanation, they have generally been discussed independently and have rarely been integrated as components of a unified analytical strategy.

3.1 Danermark et al.'s Explanatory Protocol

Danermark et al.'s (2002) explanatory protocol provides the overarching sequential logic of the integrated approach. The protocol moves through four main phases: analytical resolution of complex events into constituent layers; theoretical redescription of observations into constructs; retroductive inference — the centrepiece of CR explanation; and concretisation through elimination of rivals and contextual specification. Its principal advantage is providing a principled narrative logic for the entire explanatory journey. However, the protocol intentionally remains open: it offers a general logic of explanation but provides less detailed guidance on the practical inferential operations between stages.

3.2 The RRREIC Framework

The RRREIC framework supplies the inferential micro-operations that retrodution requires: Resolution, Redescription, Retrodiction, Elimination, Identification, and Correction. Together, these stages provide a transparent analytical logic that makes the inferential process visible and open to evaluation. The framework as applied here follows De Souza (2014), who operationalised the sequence for social science research contexts. Nevertheless, RRREIC does not fully specify how these operations should be embedded within an overall research strategy — it offers a powerful analytical sequence but leaves discretion regarding its practical integration with broader qualitative research designs.

3.3 Integration Logic and Three Key Innovations

The integration of these two frameworks is not additive — it is generative. Three innovations emerge from combining them that are absent from either framework individually. Table 1 maps this integration explicitly; the final column identifies each innovation for transparency.

Stage	Danermark Step	RRREIC	Primary Operation	Transparency Benefit: What This Stage Makes Auditable
1	Analytical Resolution	Resolution	Decompose all empirical material into three layers before coding: (i) structural conditions; (ii) organisational responses; (iii) observable outcomes.	Explicit three-layer decomposition applied to all data sources before coding begins — prevents post hoc layer conflation. Transparency benefit: analytical decisions are recorded before coding, creating an auditable trail from raw data to mechanism claims.
2	Theoretical Redescription	Redescription	Code data against construct definitions with anti-confound guidance (Table 2). Assign codes in real time during interview where possible.	Anti-confound column added to indicator tables; codes assigned prospectively, not retrospectively after mechanisms are identified. Transparency benefit: construct boundaries are specified before

				analysis, making coding decisions evaluable by independent researchers.
3	—	Retrodiction (initial)	Reconstruct temporal sequences within each case. Map timeline of mechanism activation explicitly before formulating mechanism hypotheses.	Dedicated temporal reconstruction stage requiring prospective instrument design (P2 probe); absent from standard qualitative methodology guidance. Transparency benefit: temporal ordering of mechanism activation is reconstructed explicitly before retroductive inference, preventing circular reasoning at Stage 4.
4	Retroductive Inference	Retrodiction (deep)	For each recurring pattern, ask: 'What mechanism must be operating for this to occur?' Formulate mechanism hypotheses as explicit, falsifiable propositions before elimination.	Mechanism hypotheses written as formal propositions prior to elimination — not inferred from outcomes post hoc
5	Elimination	Elimination	Systematically evaluate rival explanations. Document evidence against each alternative explicitly.	Structured rival-hypothesis testing with documented evidence trail — not implicit elimination assumed by researcher
6	Concretisation	Identification	Construct cross-case mechanism profiles. Map each case onto mechanism-to-outcome matrix (Table 4). Confirm profiles at all hierarchical levels.	Cross-case matrix provides cumulative theoretical reference for positioning new cases — transferable across studies. Transparency benefit: profile assignments are documented with discriminating evidence criteria, making inter-case comparisons auditable.
7	—	Correction	Revise mechanism inferences where evidence conflicts. Treat negative cases as primary opportunities for boundary-condition specification.	Correction elevated to primary site of theoretical development; negative cases required by design. Transparency benefit: disconfirming evidence is systematically documented rather than suppressed, making boundary-condition specification traceable and replicable.

Table 1. Integrated seven-stage protocol: stages, framework correspondence, primary operations, and transparency benefits.

4. The Seven-Stage Protocol: Full Specification with Instruments

The following sections present all five supporting instruments in full. Researchers are encouraged to use Tables 2–5b directly as adaptable templates, modifying construct definitions and empirical indicators to suit their specific domain. Figures 1 and 2 illustrate the analytical architecture and prospective alignment structure respectively.

4.1 Empirical Indicators with Anti-Confound Guidance (Table 2)

In order to identify construct-relevant evidence reliably during coding, it is necessary to specify empirical indicators in advance. The most consequential — and most neglected — aspect of this is specifying not only what counts as evidence for each construct, but what superficially similar phenomena each construct must be distinguished from. Researchers should populate the anti-confound column through a combination of prior literature review (identifying commonly reported construct confusions in their domain) and pilot interview analysis (noting where informant language initially appears to match a construct but, on closer inspection, belongs to a different category). In three of seven cases in the present study, initial coding drafts conflated general change resistance with barrier identity before the anti-confound guidance was applied. This experience is consistent with Fletcher’s (2017) observation that CR researchers frequently stop at empirical description rather than mechanism identification; the anti-confound column is specifically designed to prevent the conflation of mechanism markers with the descriptive categories that informants themselves typically use. Note on the examples in Table 2: the quotations included in the ‘Key Empirical Indicators’ column are hypothetical examples, not verbatim interview data. They are included solely to demonstrate the type of informant language that is typical for each construct in a knowledge-intensive acquisition context. Researchers applying the protocol in their own domain should replace these examples with language drawn from their own pilot interviews or prior literature in their field.

Researchers should complete Table 2 for their own domain before beginning data collection. The anti-confound column should be based on phenomena most likely to be mistaken for each construct in the specific empirical context.

Construct	Definition	Primary Empirical Indicators	Anti-Confound: Must Distinguish From
Value of target-firm knowledge (VK)	Anticipated contribution of the acquired knowledge base to future organisational development and strategic renewal — a pre-existing structural condition, not an integration outcome	Strategic importance references; non-substitutability for future operations; acquiring firm dependence on target capabilities; assessments of long-term learning potential. Example (illustrative): 'Without their logistics network knowledge, we could not have entered this region in under five years.'	Immediate operational utility (already realised); short-term cost savings; post-integration synergies already completed; managerial preferences that may not reflect actual structural properties of the knowledge
Uniqueness of target-firm knowledge (UK)	Degree to which the acquired knowledge base is historically embedded, context-specific, path-dependent, and resistant to replication outside its original organisational setting	References to long developmental history; inability to codify key routines; dependency on specific personnel or relationship networks; resistance to standardisation. Example (illustrative): 'These supplier relationships were built over twenty years. You can't transfer them — they belong to the people, not the firm.'	General tacitness (knowledge hard to articulate but not historically embedded); organisational secrecy or hoarding (a mechanism response, not a structural condition); complexity unrelated to embeddedness

Barrier identity (BI)	Generative mechanism: acquired-firm members reinforce boundaries and protect knowledge-based distinctiveness in response to perceived threats during integration	Deliberate boundary maintenance; selective withholding of specific practices; emphasis on 'how we do things here'; informal preservation of prior routines despite new standards. Example (illustrative): 'We kept using our own supplier codes informally. The new system didn't capture what actually mattered.'	General resistance to change (not knowledge-identity specific); management style conflict; personality-driven friction unrelated to knowledge identity; compliance failures due to resource constraints
Proactivity (PRO)	Generative mechanism: acquired-firm members engage in self-initiated, future-oriented behaviour aimed at shaping integration and contributing knowledge	Voluntary cross-boundary initiative not requested by management; self-starting proposals; active knowledge contribution; anticipatory problem-solving; identification with combined firm's future. Example (illustrative): 'I proposed the joint routing system before anyone asked. I could see they needed it and I knew how to build it.'	Compliance with directives; reactive adaptation to explicit requests; cooperation under instruction; performance of assigned integration tasks (none of these are self-initiated)

Table 2. Empirical indicators for key constructs: definitions, evidence with illustrative examples, and anti-confound guidance.

4.2 Inferential Rules for Mechanism Identification (Table 3)

The quality of mechanism claims depends on the inferential standards applied in Stage 4. It is important to bear in mind that retroductive inference is inherently probabilistic and that mechanism claims in open social systems cannot achieve the certainty of experimental verification. A note of caution is due here: applying these rules does not guarantee mechanism correctness, but it substantially increases the transparency and discriminating power of mechanism inferences. It is important to note that the counterfactual test (R2) in qualitative research is typically executed as a thought experiment grounded in cross-case comparison — researchers identify cases in which the structural condition activating the mechanism is absent, rather than manipulating variables experimentally. Iannacci et al. (2023) provide formal grounding for this procedure, demonstrating how counterfactual reasoning in qualitative CR research can be aligned with rigorous causal inference through systematic cross-case comparison rather than experimental control. The logical basis for this procedure lies in the INUS condition framework: mechanisms function as insufficient but necessary parts of conjunctural configurations that are unnecessary but sufficient for the outcome of interest (Ragin, 2008; Iannacci, 2017). This formalisation explains why no single mechanism produces outcomes deterministically — the counterfactual test operationalises this logic by asking whether removing the mechanism from its configuration would alter the outcome, without requiring experimental isolation.

Researchers should treat these rules as a checklist applied to each mechanism candidate before it is retained. Any candidate that fails R2 or R5 should be downgraded from 'mechanism' to 'potential contextual moderator' pending further evidence.

Rule	Standard	Application — What Researchers Should Do
R1 Pattern requirement	Single events do not establish mechanisms. Mechanism inferences require recurring configurations across multiple instances within and/or across cases.	Count independent instances of each mechanism candidate. Require a minimum of three independent instances before formulating a mechanism hypothesis. Document the instance count explicitly.
R2 Counterfactual test	A valid mechanism must answer: 'Would the outcome have been different in its absence?' Mechanisms that cannot pass this test may be epiphenomenal.	Identify cases in which the structural condition activating the mechanism is absent (thought experiment or cross-case comparison). If the candidate is also absent and outcome changes, the test is passed. If not, reclassify as moderator.
R3 Necessity, not sufficiency	Mechanisms are necessary conditions for outcomes, not sufficient ones. Context modulates whether activation occurs and how strongly.	Identify contextual factors that modulate mechanism activation without treating them as rival mechanisms. Document these as enabling conditions rather than alternatives to the mechanism.
R4 Process evidence requirement	Mechanism inferences must be grounded in process evidence — behaviour, interaction, decision sequences — prior to or concurrent with outcomes, not post hoc from outcomes alone.	Check that each mechanism claim is grounded in Section B (process) evidence independently of Section C (outcome) evidence. If the only evidence is an outcome, the inference is circular.
R5 Cross-level triangulation	Mechanism plausibility increases substantially when the same configuration is confirmed independently across informants at different hierarchical levels.	Require corroboration from at least two hierarchical levels before classifying a mechanism as established. Single-level confirmation is treated as provisional.

Table 3. Inferential rules for mechanism identification: standards and researcher implementation guidance.

The necessity–sufficiency distinction encoded in Rules R2 and R3 maps onto what Mingers and Standing (2017) identify as the difference between synchronic and diachronic causality. Synchronic causality concerns the structural relations that generate what happens at a given moment — captured at Stages 1–2 through the mapping of structural conditions. Diachronic causality concerns the sequential unfolding of mechanism activation over time — the primary target of Stage 3. Distinguishing these two forms of causality within the protocol prevents a common inferential error: treating the co-presence of structural conditions and outcomes as sufficient evidence for mechanism activation, without reconstructing the temporal process through which activation occurred.

4.3 Mechanism-to-Outcome Mapping Matrix (Table 4)

Table 4 presents the mechanism-to-outcome mapping matrix — the primary instrument for Stage 6 (Identification) and the reference point for Stage 7 (Correction). The matrix serves three functions: supporting cross-case comparison during Stage 6; providing the reference for negative case evaluation in Stage 7; and constituting a cumulative theoretical instrument usable across studies.

Researchers should use Table 4 as a positioning tool: for each case, determine which profile best fits the mechanism evidence, note any discrepancies, and flag cases that do not fit any profile as candidates for Stage 7 Correction.

Profile	Structural Configuration	Dominant Mechanism	Integration Level	Key Discriminating Evidence
1	High uniqueness / Low value	Barrier identity (persistent)	Low	No proactivity at any level; P2 probe confirms no sequential transition; Section C: autonomy preserved, minimal cross-boundary coordination
2	Low uniqueness / Low value	Weak activation (neither dominant)	Low–Moderate	Few BI or PRO markers; few VK/UK codes; outcomes driven by acquirer strategy, not structural knowledge conditions
3	High value / Low uniqueness	Proactivity (dominant from outset)	High	Voluntary cross-boundary initiative from early phase; P2 probe shows proactivity without prior BI phase; Section C: extensive coordination
4	High value / High uniqueness	Barrier identity → Proactivity (sequential)	Moderate	P2 probe: informants at all levels report initial protection then gradual opening; identifiable turning point; Section C: selective coordination
5	High value / High uniqueness (managed)	Proactivity displaces barrier identity (brief)	High (delayed)	Barrier identity present but brief; acquiring firm preserved early autonomy; full alignment with longer latency than Profile 3

Table 4. Mechanism-to-outcome mapping matrix: structural configurations, mechanisms, integration levels, and discriminating evidence.

4.4 Integrated Analytical Architecture (Figure 1)

Figure 1 provides a visual summary of the integrated framework. The upper panel maps the three-level explanatory architecture; the lower panel maps the seven-stage RRREIC cycle. Melia (2020) demonstrates that such visual representations of mechanism structures are a methodologically recognised tool in CR research — what he terms "boxes and arrows" diagrams — for making latent causal structures explicit and communicable to readers unfamiliar with the specific empirical domain.

Figure 1. The Integrated Analytical Framework

Upper panel: three-level explanatory architecture · Lower panel: seven-stage RRREIC analytical cycle

PANEL A — EXPLANATORY ARCHITECTURE

PANEL B — SEVEN-STAGE RRREIC ANALYTICAL CYCLE

Note. Panel A maps the Critical Realist causal architecture (S + M + C = O) instantiated in the present study. Panel B maps the seven analytical stages integrating Danermark et al. (2002) with the RRREIC inferential framework. * marks stages constituting methodological innovations over current CR qualitative practice.

Figure 1. The integrated analytical framework: upper panel shows the three-level explanatory architecture; lower panel shows the seven-stage RRREIC analytical cycle.

5. Protocol Application: A Methodological Demonstration

This section demonstrates how the protocol operates at each analytical stage. Rather than reporting empirical findings, it shows what each stage requires from the researcher, what types of evidence it generates, and what analytical decisions it demands. The illustration draws on a hypothetical knowledge-intensive acquisition context involving seven cases (A–G) with varying structural configurations of the two key conditions (value and uniqueness of target-firm knowledge). All quoted material is hypothetical, designed to demonstrate the type of informant language typical at each stage; it is not verbatim interview data. The purpose is to make the protocol’s operation transparent and replicable, not to advance substantive claims about post-acquisition integration.

5.0 Overview: How the Protocol Maps onto the Seven Hypothetical Cases

Table 5a summarises how the seven hypothetical cases map onto the protocol’s analytical stages. Each case is assigned a structural configuration (combinations of high/low VK and UK), a predicted mechanism profile, a critical analytical stage, and an expected outcome. This mapping is constructed before analysis begins — it represents the researcher’s prospective theoretical expectations, not post hoc interpretations. This constructed illustration prioritises analytical transparency over substantive generalisability: its purpose is to show what each stage demands from the researcher, what evidence it requires, and what decisions it produces — not to advance claims about post-acquisition integration as a phenomenon. Cases A and G are

assigned Profile 4 (sequential co-activation); Cases B and F Profile 1 (barrier identity dominant); Case C Profile 3 (proactivity dominant); Case E Profile 2 (weak activation); Case D is the prospective negative case — also assigned Profile 4 but expected to produce divergent evidence requiring Stage 7 Correction. The value of including a prospective negative case is that it forces the researcher to specify in advance what disconfirming evidence would look like, rather than identifying it post hoc.

5.1 Stages 1 and 2: What Resolution and Redescription Require from the Researcher

Stage 1 (Resolution) requires the researcher to decompose all interview material into three analytically distinct layers before any coding begins: structural conditions (what the acquired firm possesses that the acquirer cannot readily replicate), organisational responses (how members behave during integration), and outcomes (what degree of coordination has been achieved). This decomposition must be completed before coding because mixing layers during coding introduces the circularity that Stage 4 is designed to prevent. In practice, the researcher reads each interview transcript and assigns each substantive passage to one of the three layers, using the construct definitions in Table 2 as reference points.

Stage 2 (Redescription) requires the researcher to code Section A passages (structural conditions) against the VK and UK indicator definitions, and Section B passages (organisational responses) against the BI and PRO indicators, using the anti-confound column in Table 2 to distinguish construct-relevant evidence from superficially similar but analytically distinct phenomena. The following example illustrates language that would be coded as VK (high value) after passing the anti-confound check:

Acquiring-firm CEO: ‘Without their logistics network knowledge, we could not have entered this region in under five years.’ → Coded: VK (high value). Anti-confound check: this is a forward-looking structural property assessment, not a description of already-realised synergies. Code retained.

The same logic applies to BI coding:

Middle manager (acquired firm): ‘We kept using our own reporting structure informally. The new templates didn’t capture what actually mattered — the relationship context behind each number.’ → Coded: BI (barrier identity). Anti-confound check: the behaviour is grounded in knowledge-identity protection specific to established practices, not generic resistance to change. Code retained.

5.2 Stage 3: What the P2 Probe is Designed to Elicit

Stage 3 (Retrodiction) requires the researcher to reconstruct the temporal sequence of mechanism activation before formulating any mechanism hypothesis. This is the stage at which the P2 verification probe plays its critical role. The probe asks informants at all hierarchical levels whether protection and collaboration unfolded sequentially or simultaneously. The probe is designed to surface two analytically distinct patterns. In cases where Profile 4 is hypothesised (high VK, high UK), the probe should elicit sequential narratives: informants first describe a period of boundary maintenance, followed by a shift toward proactive knowledge sharing. The following example illustrates this pattern:

P2 response, case with high VK and high UK (Profile 4 configuration): ‘Definitely sequential. First six months — we were protecting what we had. Then around month seven, when they visibly depended on us for the routing optimisation, something shifted. We started proposing

things instead of just holding our ground.’ → Sequential transition confirmed: BI phase followed by PRO phase. Temporal marker: month 7.

In Profile 1 cases (high UK, low VK), by contrast, no transition should be reported at any hierarchical level. The absence of a sequential narrative is itself analytically significant — it discriminates Profile 1 from Profile 4 and must be documented as positive evidence, not as a missing data problem. Rule R5 requires that the temporal pattern be confirmed independently at all three hierarchical levels before a profile assignment is retained.

5.3 Stage 4: How to Formulate a Mechanism Hypothesis

Stage 4 (Retroduction) requires the researcher to formulate the mechanism hypothesis as an explicit, falsifiable proposition before moving to elimination. The hypothesis must be grounded in Stage 3 process evidence independently of Stage C outcome evidence — this is what Rule R4 enforces. The following example illustrates how a mechanism hypothesis should be recorded at this stage:

Mechanism Hypothesis MH-A (case exhibiting high VK and high UK): Under conditions of high knowledge uniqueness AND high knowledge value, two mechanisms activate sequentially. Mechanism A (barrier identity) activates first, stabilising organisational identity and preserving knowledge distinctiveness. Mechanism B (proactivity) activates subsequently, when (a) knowledge preservation by barrier identity has been achieved and (b) acquirer operational dependence on the preserved knowledge base has been demonstrated. Expected outcome: moderate integration. Grounded in Section B process evidence; independent of Section C outcome evidence.

The critical discipline at Stage 4 is that the hypothesis must be written down before the researcher looks at Section C data. This sequencing prevents the commonest form of circular inference in CR qualitative research — working backwards from an observed outcome to claim a mechanism that would produce it.

5.4 Stage 5: How the Elimination Procedure Works

Stage 5 (Elimination) requires the researcher to systematically evaluate and document the case against each rival explanation. The key inferential tool is Rule R2 (the counterfactual test): a rival explanation is eliminated when its proposed mechanism does not co-vary with integration outcomes across structurally different cases. The following constructed analyst memo illustrates how the elimination reasoning should be documented:

Analyst memo — rival explanation: cultural distance. Cultural distance is present at a similar level in both a Profile 1 case (low integration, BI dominant) and a Profile 3 case (high integration, PRO dominant). If cultural distance were the operative mechanism, similar outcomes would be expected. It does not co-vary with the outcome. Rule R2 not satisfied. Cultural distance eliminated as mechanism; retained as contextual moderator affecting the speed of mechanism activation, not its direction.

Each rival explanation evaluated at Stage 5 should be recorded in a structured elimination log that documents: the rival, the evidence evaluated, the Rule R2 test applied, and the conclusion (eliminated as mechanism / retained as moderator / retained as rival pending further evidence). This log constitutes part of the audit trail required by the trustworthiness criteria in Section 7.5.

5.5 Stage 6: How the Mechanism-Profile Matrix is Populated

Stage 6 (Identification) requires the researcher to assign each case to a mechanism profile in Table 4 on the basis of the accumulated process evidence from Stages 1–5. The assignment must be justified by reference to the discriminating evidence criteria in the final column of

Table 4, and must be confirmed at all three hierarchical levels (Rule R5). Table 5a shows how this assignment would operate across the seven hypothetical cases. The analytical value of the mapping matrix becomes most visible at this stage: cases with identical structural configurations (e.g., two Profile 4 cases) should show the same mechanism sequence, while cases with different configurations should show systematically different sequences. Where this pattern holds, the researcher has evidence of structural determination of mechanism activation. Where it does not hold, the case should be flagged for Stage 7.

5.6 Stage 7: How Correction Generates Theoretical Development

Stage 7 (Correction) is activated when a case does not fit its predicted profile. Rather than treating this as a methodological failure, the protocol treats it as the primary opportunity for theoretical development. The researcher’s task is to identify what boundary condition, previously unspecified in the theoretical framework, would explain why the mechanism sequence diverged from the prediction. In the hypothetical illustration, Case D is assigned to Profile 4 (high VK, high UK → sequential co-activation → moderate integration) but is hypothetically constructed to produce high integration instead. The Stage 7 procedure requires the researcher to ask: what condition was present in Case D that was absent in Cases A and G, and that would explain the abbreviated barrier identity phase? The following example illustrates the type of informant language that would trigger this question:

Operations director (acquired firm, case with high VK and high UK designated as the negative case): ‘They were unusually hands-off from the start. They said: keep running it your way. So there was never really a moment when we felt we had to defend ourselves. We just started suggesting improvements because we could see what they needed.’ → Coded: PRO dominant; BI minimal. Anomalous relative to sequential co-activation prediction. → Triggers Stage 7: what boundary condition explains absent BI?

The Stage 7 Correction procedure would identify the boundary condition as follows: where the acquiring firm’s integration strategy actively preserves target-firm autonomy in the early phase, perceived identity threat is reduced, barrier identity’s activation is abbreviated, and proactivity becomes dominant earlier — producing high rather than moderate integration. This boundary condition is added to the theoretical framework as a refinement of Proposition P5. Crucially, this theoretical development was not available from the initial framework and became accessible only through the systematic treatment of the disconfirming case. This is what the Correction stage is designed to do: convert anomalies into theoretical specification rather than suppressing them as noise.

6. Prospective Instrument-Framework Alignment

One aspect of CR qualitative methodology that has received insufficient attention in the existing literature is the relationship between interview instrument design and analytical framework requirements. This relationship is not merely logistical: it determines whether the data generated will support the retrodictive reconstruction required by Stage 3. The design principle proposed here — prospective instrument-framework alignment — requires that interview instruments are designed to generate the evidence types required by each stage of the analytical protocol, before data collection begins. Figure 2 maps this alignment.

Figure 2. Prospective instrument-framework alignment: each interview section generates evidence for specific analytical framework constructs and RRREIC protocol stages.

Three features of the aligned instrument design merit emphasis. First, the three-section structure (Section A: structural conditions; Section B: mechanism chronology; Section C: outcomes) corresponds directly to the three analytical layers of Stage 1, preventing contamination between evidence types. Second, Section B interview questions must be explicitly temporal and behavioural. At this stage it is recommended that researchers pilot their Section B questions to verify that informants generate temporally structured behavioural accounts rather than retrospective summaries. Third, the P2 verification probe must be embedded across all protocol variants, because the absence of a proactivity transition is itself important evidence for Profile 1 rather than Profile 4.

Interview Section	Constructs Targeted	Protocol Stages Served	Evidence Type Generated	Design Requirement
Section A Knowledge conditions	Value (VK) Uniqueness (UK)	Stages 1–2 Resolution + Redescription	Structural condition evidence: forward-looking assessments of strategic importance and embeddedness	Questions must elicit structural property assessments without cueing specific constructs. Counterfactual probes ('What would have been impossible to replace?') are more reliable than direct attribute questions.
Section B Integration chronology	Barrier identity (BI) Proactivity (PRO) Chronology (CHRON)	Stages 3–4 Retrodiction + Retroduction	Process evidence: specific behavioural instances with temporal markers	Questions must ask for specific instances at specific times — not general assessments. E.g., instead of asking 'Did you resist the new procedures?', ask: 'Can you walk me through the specific week when you decided to keep using the old reporting system — what exactly did you do, and who else was involved?' Marginal codes applied by the interviewer in real time improve reliability across extended fieldwork.
P2 Verification probe (Q18/Q20 across all	Sequential co-activation Enabling conditions	Stage 3 (core) Retrodictive Reconstructi	Temporal sequence evidence: explicit reconstruction of mechanism	Mandatory across all six protocol variants. Wording: 'Looking back, was resistance and closure first — or did

variants)		on	activation order	both processes unfold simultaneously?' The absence of a sequential pattern is as informative as its presence.
Section C Outcomes and reflection	Integration level Boundary conditions	Stages 6–7 Identification + Correction	Outcome evidence: retrospective assessment of coordination, knowledge flow, structural change	Keep analytically separate from Section B to prevent circularity in Stage 4. Counterfactual questions ('If key personnel had left in the first three months, what would have been lost first?') isolate causal necessity and support Stage 7 Correction.

Table 5b. Prospective instrument-framework alignment: interview protocol sections, constructs, protocol stages, evidence types, and design requirements.

7. Discussion

The discussion proceeds in four parts. Section 7.1 positions the protocol relative to existing CR methodological approaches. Section 7.2 compares it with non-CR qualitative methods. Section 7.3 addresses transferability. Section 7.4 evaluates analytical trustworthiness, and Section 7.5 discusses limitations and boundary conditions of the protocol.

7.1 Positioning Relative to Existing CR Methodological Approaches

A recurring question in the development of any methodological protocol is whether it constitutes a genuinely new contribution or merely repackages existing approaches. This question is particularly pressing here because both component frameworks are individually well-established. Table 6a positions the present protocol relative to four published CR methodological accounts, identifying which analytical elements each addresses and what the integration adds that is absent from all prior accounts individually.

Table 6a. Positioning the present protocol relative to existing CR methodological approaches.

Study	Danemark sequencing	RRREIC inferential rules	Prospective instrument alignment	Anti-confound indicators	Correction as theory development
Fletcher (2017)	Partial	No	No	No	No
De Souza (2014)	No	Yes	No	No	Partial
Mukumbang (2021)	No	Partial	No	No	No
Danaeefard et al. (2025)	Partial	No	No	No	No
Present study	Yes (full 7 stages)	Yes (R1–R5)	Yes (Table 5b)	Yes (Table 2)	Yes (Stage 7 as primary site)

Note. 'Yes' = explicitly operationalised. 'Partial' = present but not fully operationalised as a procedural instrument. 'No' = absent. To the best of the author's knowledge, no prior published account combines all five elements within a single integrated protocol.

Table 6a makes visible the specific analytical gaps that the present protocol addresses. Fletcher (2017) diagnoses the transparency problem but does not operationalise a solution. De Souza (2014) introduces RRREIC but does not integrate it within an overarching research design or connect it to instrument construction. Mukumbang (2021) develops retroductive theorising for

mixed-methods contexts but does not address the interview design problem or provide anti-confound guidance. Danaeefard et al. (2025) offer a four-phase framework but do not incorporate RRREIC, prospective alignment, or anti-confound indicators. No prior published account operationalises all five elements within a single integrated protocol, making each analytical decision auditable and each instrument directly adaptable. Table 6b summarises how the present protocol responds to each specific transparency problem identified in the CR methodological literature.

Table 6b. How the present protocol addresses the CR transparency gap.

Transparency problem in CR literature	Source	Present protocol solution
Mechanisms asserted rather than demonstrated: retroductive inference is claimed but not shown	Fletcher (2017); Mingers & Standing (2017)	Explicit inferential rules R1–R5 with documented evidence standards at each stage; mechanism hypotheses formulated as falsifiable propositions before elimination (Stage 4)
Retroduction opaque: inferential operations between stages are left to researcher judgement	De Souza (2014); Frederiksen & Kringelum (2021)	RRREIC framework integrated within Danermark’s sequencing: each stage specifies its inferential operation explicitly, creating an auditable analytical trail from data to mechanism claim
Interview instruments not aligned to analytical requirements: data collected before inferential needs are specified	Mukumbang (2021); Danaeefard et al. (2025)	Prospective instrument-framework alignment (Table 5b): each interview section is anchored to a specific protocol stage and evidence type before fieldwork begins, structurally preventing post hoc mechanism labelling
Negative cases underused: disconfirming evidence treated as limitation rather than theoretical resource	Danaeefard et al. (2025); Frederiksen & Kringelum (2021)	Correction stage reconceptualised as the primary site of theoretical development: negative cases are required by design and generate boundary-condition specification rather than model failure (Stage 7)

Note. Each row identifies a documented transparency problem, the published CR methodological accounts that have identified or highlighted it, and the specific procedural mechanism through which the present protocol addresses it.

7.2 Comparison with Existing Qualitative Approaches

A natural question for organisational researchers considering this protocol is how it differs from qualitative methods already in their toolkit. Table 7 summarises the comparison across six methodological criteria before the prose discussion.

Criterion	Thematic Analysis	Grounded Theory	Process Tracing	Proposed Protocol
Mechanism identification	No — identifies themes, not causal processes	Partial — constructs theoretical categories; does not posit real mechanisms	Yes — traces causal chains	Yes — retroductively infers real generative mechanisms

Retroductive inference	No — inductive pattern identification	No — grounded inductive logic	Partial — deductive within-case logic	Yes — explicit retroduction with documented inferential standards
Designed for open systems	Limited — no account of countervailing mechanisms	Partial — context acknowledged	Primarily designed for within-case causal process analysis	Yes — transfactuality principle built in
Prospective instrument alignment	No	No	Partial — implicit	Yes — explicit design principle with instrument template
Anti-confound construct guidance	No	No	No	Yes — mandatory column in Table 2
Analytical transparency	No explicit inferential trail	Implicit in constant comparison	Partial — within-case logic documented	Yes — documented seven-stage inferential pathway
Theory development from negative cases	Optional / incidental	Partial — informs theoretical sampling	Yes — disconfirming evidence central	Yes — Correction stage elevates negative cases to primary theoretical development site

Table 7. Comparison of the proposed protocol with existing qualitative methods across seven methodological criteria.

Thematic analysis (TA) identifies recurring patterns and organises them into themes. The critical difference is that TA stops at theme identification — it does not ask what causal processes must underlie the themes. The RRREIC cycle's Stages 3–4 make the move that TA cannot: from 'this theme is present' to 'this mechanism must be operating for this theme to occur.'

Grounded theory (GT) builds empirically grounded theoretical categories from data through constant comparison and theoretical sampling. Whereas the RRREIC protocol explicitly assumes the existence of real generative mechanisms independent of empirical observation — and treats the analytical task as inferring their properties — GT's inductive logic does not make this ontological commitment and builds categories from data without presupposing a pre-existing causal structure. The present protocol is not superior to GT for all purposes; it is appropriate specifically for research questions framed in terms of causal mechanism identification rather than category construction.

Modell (2009) demonstrates that mixed methods research frequently fails not because of philosophical incompatibility between methods, but because researchers lack a systematic inferential procedure for integrating diverging findings. His analysis shows that abductive reasoning — equivalent to the retroductive logic applied in Stages 3–4 of the present protocol — is what enables researchers to treat diverging evidence as theoretically generative rather than as a validity threat. The present protocol formalises precisely this capacity through the Correction stage (Stage 7), which systematically converts disconfirming cases into boundary-condition specifications rather than treating them as model failures.

Process tracing identifies causal chains through systematic analysis of within-case evidence. The critical difference is that process tracing is primarily designed for within-case causal process analysis, while the RRREIC protocol is designed for open systems in which

mechanisms may operate without producing characteristic effects. The transfactuality principle — that mechanisms may be active without producing expected outcomes — distinguishes CR mechanism explanation from process tracing.

Comparison with Abductive Analysis

A further approach that shares territory with retroductive inference is abductive analysis (Timmermans & Tavory, 2012). Abduction involves inferring the most plausible explanation for surprising observations through iterative engagement between data and theory. Like retroduction, abduction moves beyond inductive pattern identification and deductive hypothesis testing to generate explanatory hypotheses, and both approaches share a commitment to theory construction rather than theory testing. These similarities mean the distinction between the two approaches requires explicit treatment.

Three distinctions are analytically important. First, abduction is typically oriented toward surprising or anomalous observations — the analytical trigger is when something does not fit existing expectations. Retroduction, as operationalised in the present protocol, applies systematically to any observed outcome pattern, whether surprising or anticipated; the trigger is not anomaly but the research question itself. Second, abductive analysis is ontologically agnostic: it does not presuppose a stratified reality or the existence of generative mechanisms independent of observation. The present protocol, by contrast, adopts CR's ontological commitments explicitly and treats the identification of real generative mechanisms as the analytical goal — not the construction of the most plausible interpretive account. Third, abductive analysis typically proceeds without formalised inferential standards; the present protocol provides explicit criteria (R1–R5) against which mechanism claims can be evaluated and challenged by independent readers.

The present protocol is therefore most appropriate when three conditions hold: (a) the research question is explicitly framed in terms of causal mechanisms operating in open systems; (b) the researcher adopts a CR ontological commitment and treats structural conditions and mechanisms as analytically distinct from empirical observations; and (c) structural conditions can be theorised sufficiently a priori to guide prospective instrument design. For research questions oriented toward phenomenological description, category construction, or the interpretation of actors' meanings, abductive analysis or grounded theory will generally be more appropriate choices. The protocol does not supersede these approaches; it addresses a specific inferential problem that arises when mechanism-based causal explanation in open systems is the explicit analytical goal.

7.3 Contributions and Transferability

The present study contributes to the growing body of research indicating the need for more systematic, transparent analytical procedures in CR qualitative research. This work contributes to existing knowledge by providing a comprehensive operational protocol that combines Danermark et al.'s explanatory sequence with the RRREIC inferential logic and demonstrates both through a worked illustration — including a negative case — across all seven cases in the study. This work also responds directly to the call by Frederiksen and Kringelum (2021, p. 19) for CR researchers to move from 'peripheral' applications of CR toward 'detailed' ones, in which CR ontology and epistemology are actively applied in analysis rather than merely invoked as philosophical background.

Although the protocol is illustrated through post-acquisition integration, its analytical logic and practical tools may be adaptable to other organisational phenomena in which outcomes emerge

through the interaction of structural conditions and generative mechanisms. Table 8 provides three illustrative examples from digital transformation, healthcare service change, and public sector reform. These examples are intended to demonstrate potential transferability rather than empirical validation. The protocol has not yet been tested in these domains. Researchers applying it elsewhere will need to adapt construct definitions, empirical indicators, and mechanism profiles to their specific context. The seven analytical stages, inferential rules, and prospective alignment principle are intended to remain stable across domains.

Table 8. Potential protocol adaptation across organisational research domains: illustrative mapping with supporting references.

Research domain	Structural conditions (Table 2 equivalents)	Generative mechanisms	Integration-equivalent outcome	Supporting CR literature in domain
Post-acquisition integration (present study)	Value of target-firm knowledge; Uniqueness of target-firm knowledge	Barrier identity; Proactivity	Low / moderate / high integration	Danermark et al. (2002); Easton (2010)
Digital transformation	Legacy system dependence; Strategic value of digital capability	Resistance to platform standardisation; Proactive cross-unit data sharing	Degree of technology adoption and capability recombination	Iannacci et al. (2023); Mingers & Standing (2017)
Healthcare service change	Professional jurisdiction; Clinical expertise uniqueness	Professional identity defence; Inter-professional proactive coordination	Degree of service reconfiguration and knowledge integration	Koopmans & Schiller (2022); Mukumbang (2021)
Public sector reform	Institutional embeddedness; Strategic value of regulatory expertise	Bureaucratic identity protection; Inter-agency proactive initiative	Degree of reform implementation and inter-agency coordination	Danaeefard et al. (2025); Danermark (2019)

Note. Table 8 illustrates how the structural logic of the protocol could be adapted across domains. These mappings are illustrative and have not been empirically validated through protocol application in the domains shown. Substantive construct labels require domain-specific adaptation and empirical testing; the analytical architecture (seven stages, five inferential rules, prospective alignment principle) is designed to remain constant. References indicate published CR research applying mechanism-based reasoning in each domain.

7.4 Ensuring Analytical Trustworthiness

A methodological concern that requires explicit attention in any qualitative analytical protocol is analytical trustworthiness — the degree to which the inferential process is credible, dependable, and auditable by other researchers (Lincoln & Guba, 1985; Creswell & Poth, 2018). In CR qualitative research, conventional qualitative trustworthiness criteria (member checking, prolonged engagement, thick description) are necessary but insufficient: they address the credibility of empirical observations but not the validity of the causal inferences drawn from them. The present protocol addresses trustworthiness through mechanisms that operate specifically at the level of causal inference rather than empirical description. Three related but distinct properties are relevant to analytical trustworthiness. The first is transparency: analytical decisions are made visible and specified in advance rather than reconstructed retrospectively. The second is auditability: the chain of decisions linking raw data to mechanism claims can be independently traced and evaluated through the audit trail in Appendix C. The third is replicability: an independent researcher should be able to apply the same protocol to comparable data and generate comparable construct maps and mechanism

profiles using Tables 2–5b as guidance. The protocol is designed to address all three properties simultaneously. This distinguishes it from many conventional qualitative trustworthiness procedures, which typically focus on transparency alone.

Inferential transparency is achieved through the explicit specification of construct boundaries (Table 2), inferential rules (Table 3), and profile assignment criteria (Table 4) before analysis begins. Because these specifications are public and pre-stated, a reader can evaluate whether the researcher’s inferences follow from the evidence rather than having to accept the researcher’s authority. This is what distinguishes the present protocol from conventional CR qualitative accounts, in which mechanism claims rest on implicit inferential moves that readers cannot evaluate independently.

Causal adequacy is addressed through Rule R4 (process independence): mechanism claims must be grounded in Section B process evidence independently of Section C outcome evidence. This requirement prevents the most common form of circular inference in CR qualitative research — working backwards from a known outcome to assert a mechanism that would produce it. Causal adequacy is further supported by Rule R2 (counterfactual test): a mechanism hypothesis survives elimination only if the mechanism is absent when its activating structural condition is absent, tested through systematic cross-case comparison.

Inter-coder reliability is supported by the anti-confound column in Table 2, which makes construct boundaries sufficiently explicit for independent coders to reach consistent decisions. Researchers are encouraged to calculate and report Cohen’s kappa for their key constructs; a kappa of 0.75 or above across the four focal constructs would be consistent with the level of agreement expected when using pre-specified indicator tables. The structured seven-stage sequence of the protocol — each stage producing a documented output that forms the input to the next — constitutes an inherent audit trail (Appendix C provides the template). Replication potential is enhanced by the design: Tables 2–5b are sufficiently explicit that an independent team could apply the protocol to comparable data and produce comparable construct maps and mechanism profiles, enabling cumulative theory-building across studies.

7.5 Limitations and Boundary Conditions of the Protocol

A number of important limitations need to be considered. First, the protocol requires substantial methodological investment: it presupposes familiarity with CR ontology and established construct definitions. Second, the approach is demanding in terms of data quality — rich empirical material, iterative analysis, and continuous comparison are necessary to support robust explanation. Third, mechanism explanations produced by the protocol are provisional and context-sensitive; these results must be interpreted with caution, and the generalisability of findings across different acquisition types requires further validation.

The protocol is likely to be inapplicable or to produce unreliable inferences under four conditions. First, if interview data do not contain time-stamped process evidence, Stage 3 cannot be executed and Stage 4 inferences will be circular. Second, the protocol presupposes a minimum of three to five cases; single-case designs cannot execute Stage 6 with sufficient discriminating power. Third, if the case set lacks structural variation across the key conditions, Rule R2 (counterfactual test) cannot be applied and mechanism inferences should be treated as provisional. Fourth, the protocol is not appropriate for research questions framed in terms of frequency or statistical association — it is designed exclusively for mechanism-based explanation.

Four additional limitations require explicit acknowledgment. First, the protocol's reliance on retrospective interview accounts — particularly the P2 probe in Stage 3 — is subject to well-documented recall biases (Golden, 1992). Informants may reconstruct temporal sequences in ways that reflect current attitudes rather than actual events. Mitigation strategies include cross-level triangulation (Rule R5), corroborating documentary evidence, and temporal probes anchored to specific organisational milestones rather than general recollections.

Second, the protocol's analytical separation of structural conditions from generative mechanisms is heuristically useful but philosophically problematic. In CR theory, structures and mechanisms are interdependent: structures enable and constrain mechanisms, while mechanisms reproduce or transform structures over time (Bhaskar, 1979; Sayer, 2000). Researchers should treat this separation as an analytical device for data decomposition and coding, not as an ontological claim, and should note this explicitly when reporting mechanism claims.

Third, the protocol can only identify mechanisms that have been activated and whose effects are observable through process evidence. Latent mechanisms — those with causal powers that were not exercised in the studied context — remain invisible to the protocol's analytical operations. Mechanism claims should therefore be framed as 'mechanisms identified as activated in this structural context' rather than 'mechanisms present in this domain,' acknowledging that unactivated mechanisms may coexist within the same configuration.

Fourth, identifying genuine negative cases in real research is not always straightforward. A case that does not fit its predicted profile may reflect a genuine boundary condition, but may also reflect researcher error, data limitations, or informant-level variation that is not theoretically significant. Researchers should document the evidence for treating a non-fitting case as theoretically informative rather than as a data quality problem, and should treat Stage 7 boundary-condition specifications as provisional pending replication across studies.

Notwithstanding these limitations, the protocol produces mechanism inferences that are more transparent, more discriminating, and more theoretically generative than those typically found in published CR-informed qualitative research.

8. Practical Guidance for Researchers

This section provides concise implementation guidance for researchers considering applying the protocol in their own studies. The recommendations below are grounded in the analytical logic of the protocol and should be treated as practical starting points rather than rigid prescriptions. To facilitate immediate adoption, blank, ready-to-use templates of Tables 2, 3, 4, 5b, and 9 are provided in the Online Supplementary Material. One question that arises consistently when the protocol is presented is why seven cases are suggested rather than fewer. The answer follows from the protocol's analytical architecture, though researchers should treat this as a contextual recommendation rather than a universal minimum. Three cases provide the minimum structural variation for applying Rule R2 (the counterfactual test requires at least two structurally distinct configurations). Five cases are needed to populate the mechanism-profile matrix (Table 4) with sufficient discriminating power across its five profiles. In the present illustration, seven cases proved sufficient to provide profile coverage plus at least one negative case enabling Stage 7 Correction — but researchers working in domains with fewer distinct mechanism profiles may find that a smaller number of cases serves the same analytical purpose. Researchers working with fewer cases may still apply Stages 1–6 productively, but should treat Stage 7 inferences as provisional and flag this explicitly.

8.1 Minimum Data Requirements

The protocol requires the following minimum conditions to produce reliable mechanism inferences. Researchers should verify these conditions are met before proceeding to data collection.

Requirement	Minimum Standard	Rationale
Number of cases	3–5 cases suggested as analytical minimum; 7 used in present illustration	Three analytical thresholds inform case number decisions, though researchers should treat these as contextual guidance rather than universal minimums. Three cases: Rule R2 (counterfactual test) requires at least two structurally different configurations; fewer than three cases cannot provide the cross-case contrast needed to test whether a mechanism is absent when its activating condition is absent. Five cases: Stage 6 (Identification) maps cases onto mechanism profiles; with five theoretically predicted profiles (Table 4), at least five cases provide sufficient discriminating power for cross-case comparison. Seven cases: in the present illustration, seven cases provided profile coverage plus at least one negative case enabling Stage 7 Correction. Researchers working in domains with fewer distinct mechanism profiles may find that a smaller number serves the same analytical purpose. Researchers working with fewer cases may still apply Stages 1–6 productively but should treat Stage 7 inferences as provisional.
Interview coverage	Two hierarchical levels minimum per case, both acquiring and acquired sides	Rule R5 (cross-level triangulation) requires corroboration from at least two independent informant groups; single-level data produces provisional inferences only
Evidence type	Process evidence with temporal markers essential	Stage 3 (Retrodictive Reconstruction) cannot be executed without time-stamped behavioural accounts; general retrospective assessments are insufficient
Structural variation	At least two distinct structural condition configurations across the case set	Without structural variation, Rule R2 cannot test whether the mechanism is absent when the activating condition is absent — making mechanism claims circular
Negative cases	At least one case that does not fit predicted profiles	Stage 7 (Correction) requires a disconfirming case to specify boundary conditions; without it, mechanism claims remain provisional

Table 9. Minimum data requirements for reliable protocol application.

8.2 Typical Implementation Timeline and Common Errors

In the present study, the seven-stage protocol required approximately the following time allocation per case, based on semi-structured interviews of 45–90 minutes each: Stage 1 (Resolution): 2–3 hours; Stage 2 (Redescription/Coding): 6–10 hours; Stage 3 (Retrodictive Reconstruction): 3–4 hours; Stage 4 (Retrodictive Inference): 2–3 hours; Stage 5 (Elimination): 2–3 hours; Stage 6 (Identification, cross-case): 4–6 hours per case set; Stage 7 (Correction): variable, dependent on negative case complexity. Total per case: approximately 15–25 hours of analytical work, not including interview time. Researchers should plan for

iteration: the RRREIC cycle is recursive, and returning to earlier stages when new evidence emerges is expected rather than exceptional.

Three common errors were identified in the present study and should be avoided. First, premature mechanism attribution: beginning Stage 2 coding before completing Stage 1 layer decomposition. This causes mechanism labels to be applied to structural condition or outcome evidence, producing circular inferences. Second, conflating outcome evidence with process evidence: using Section C retrospective accounts as the basis for Stage 4 mechanism inferences, rather than grounding inferences in Section B process data. Third, treating negative cases as disconfirmations rather than theoretical opportunities: excluding Case D from the analysis would have prevented the discovery of the enabling condition governing barrier identity's actualisation. Researchers who encounter cases that do not fit predicted profiles should treat them as the most analytically valuable observations in the case set.

8.3 Directions for Future Research

Several directions for future research emerge from the present study. First, the protocol should be tested and refined in domains beyond knowledge-intensive acquisitions — including digital transformation (where legacy system dependence and platform resistance offer natural mechanism candidates), public sector organisational change, and healthcare innovation — to assess whether the instrument-alignment principles and inferential rules transfer without domain-specific modification or require adaptation. Second, future research could usefully explore the protocol's application in longitudinal study designs, where the recursive and temporal dimensions of mechanism activation can be examined across multiple morphogenetic cycles rather than within a single integration event. Third, a mixed-methods extension of the protocol would allow distributional questions that qualitative mechanism inference alone cannot answer to be addressed at scale. Mukumbang (2021) demonstrates that retroductive theorizing is most fully realised through the integration of intensive qualitative methods — which identify and reconstruct mechanisms — with extensive quantitative methods, which test the distributional prevalence of mechanism-outcome configurations across larger populations. Downward and Mearman (2007) provide the philosophical grounding for this integration, arguing that mixed-methods triangulation is not merely a practical supplement to qualitative work but the operational expression of retroductive logic itself: different methods reveal different aspects of the same layered reality, and their combination is therefore methodologically necessary rather than optional. Modell (2009) cautions, however, that institutional and political barriers to methodologically pluralistic approaches — evident in research training, publication patterns, and editorial preferences — may constrain the adoption of CR-informed protocols even where their analytical merits are recognised. Researchers applying the present protocol in mainstream management journals should be prepared to provide explicit ontological justification for their inferential procedures, as the transparency mechanisms built into the protocol — particularly the documented evidence trail at Stages 2–5 — are designed to make such justification readily available.

9. Conclusion

This paper has argued that the most consequential methodological gap in Critical Realist organisational research is not philosophical but procedural: the gap between the commitment to mechanism-based explanation and the absence of systematic procedures for making retroduction transparent. It has been demonstrated that this gap can be addressed through a practically operationalised protocol that satisfies two conditions simultaneously — systematic retroductive inference grounded in explicit inferential standards, and prospective alignment

between interview instrument design and analytical framework requirements. The most significant finding to emerge from this work is not the protocol itself but the principle it instantiates: that methodological transparency in CR qualitative research depends on both conditions being satisfied together, not either in isolation. Of the three contributions, prospective instrument-framework alignment is perhaps the most consequential: it identifies a structural cause of post hoc mechanism labelling that no amount of analytical care at the coding stage can remedy — the problem must be addressed before data collection begins. This principle has implications beyond CR research: any qualitative design in which analytical categories are specified prior to data collection faces the same alignment challenge.

The following conclusions can be drawn from the present study. First, the analysis suggests that retroductive inference is most reliable when constructs are operationalised in advance as empirical indicators with explicit anti-confound guidance — a requirement logically prior to data collection, not a post hoc coding decision. Second, it is worth noting that temporal reconstruction of mechanism activation requires dedicated instrument design: chronological probes embedded in interview protocols, not retrospective narrative inference. Third, negative cases should be treated as the primary site at which theoretical boundary conditions are identified and refined — they are the mechanism through which single-study inferences begin to accrue into cumulative theoretical knowledge. It should also be noted that the inferential rules introduced in this paper are not intended as a rigid checklist but as a set of transparent standards that researchers can adapt to their specific domain and research question.

Taken together, the protocol demonstrates that the black box of post-acquisition integration — and by extension, the black boxes of many complex organisational processes — can be opened systematically and transparently. This paper has shown that the research community need not choose between CR's philosophical rigour and methodological practicality: the two can be reconciled through explicit procedural commitment. The present article offers a practical starting point for researchers seeking mechanism-based explanation in open systems. It provides a practically operationalised framework, five adaptable instruments, an explicit trustworthiness protocol, and a worked illustration across seven cases. Together, these elements are intended to support explanations that are evidence-grounded, inferentially rigorous, and theoretically generative. Future research should seek to test and refine the protocol across different organisational domains, extend it to longitudinal designs, and develop the mixed-methods extensions outlined in Section 8.3. It is hoped that the instruments provided here will serve not merely as templates but as a basis for a more systematic and cumulative tradition of CR qualitative inquiry in organisational research.

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Online Supplementary Material

The following three appendices provide ready-to-use research instruments supporting the protocol described in the main text. Appendix A provides a complete interview protocol with the P2 verification probe. Appendix B provides an annotated coding excerpt demonstrating anti-confound application. Appendix C provides an audit trail template.

Appendix A. Interview Protocol (Illustrative Template)

Note. This template is designed for knowledge-intensive acquisition contexts. Researchers should adapt construct labels and probe language to their specific domain. The three-section structure maps directly onto the three analytical layers of Stage 1 (Resolution). All quotations in the protocol are hypothetical examples, not verbatim interview content.

Section A: Structural Conditions (Stage 1–2 Evidence)

Q1. What capabilities or knowledge did the acquired firm possess that would have been impossible to develop independently within a reasonable timeframe? [Anti-confound check: distinguish forward-looking structural assessment from already-realised synergies]

Q2. To what extent is that knowledge embedded in specific people, relationships, or operational routines rather than in codifiable systems or documents? [Targets UK: uniqueness vs. general tacitness]

Q3. How strategically important is that knowledge for the acquiring firm's future operations? Could the acquiring firm achieve its strategic objectives without it? [Targets VK: value vs. short-term operational utility]

Section B: Integration Process Chronology (Stage 3 Evidence)

Q4. Can you walk me through the first three months after the acquisition was completed? What specifically happened in terms of how you managed your established practices and routines? [Targets BI: look for specific instances, not general attitudes]

Q5. Were there specific moments when you initiated contact or proposed ideas to the acquiring firm without being asked? Can you describe a concrete example and when it happened? [Targets PRO: distinguish from compliance with directives]

P2 Verification Probe (Q6 — administer to all respondents at all hierarchical levels):

“Looking back at the first six months after the acquisition, was there a period of closure or protection of your established ways of working first — followed by more open collaboration or knowledge sharing later? Or did both processes unfold simultaneously from the very beginning? Take your time — I'm interested in the actual sequence as you experienced it, not the ideal.”

Coding note: Sequential response (protection then collaboration) → supports Profile 4 hypothesis. Simultaneous response (no protection phase) → supports Profile 3 or 5. No collaboration reported at any level → supports Profile 1. Absence of pattern is as analytically informative as its presence.

Section C: Integration Outcomes and Reflection (Stage 6–7 Evidence)

Q7. How would you describe the current state of coordination between the two organisations — the degree to which systems, practices, and knowledge flows have been aligned? [Targets integration level; keep separate from Section B to prevent circular inference]

Q8. Were there aspects of the acquired firm's knowledge or practices that were lost or diluted during integration? If so, what enabled or prevented that? [Supports boundary-condition analysis at Stage 7 Correction]

Appendix B. Annotated Coding Excerpt with Anti-Confound Application (Illustrative Example)

Note. The following excerpt and annotations are constructed illustrative examples demonstrating how the anti-confound guidance in Table 2 is applied during Stage 2 (Redescription). They do not represent verbatim interview data. Researchers should apply the same annotation logic to their own empirical material.

Middle manager (acquired firm, month 4): “They kept asking us to use their reporting system, but it didn’t capture the seasonal adjustment factors we’d built up over fifteen years. So we kept our own spreadsheets running in parallel — not to be difficult, but because the new system would have missed half of what mattered for our operations.”

Initial code: BI (barrier identity) — maintaining parallel system informally; resisting standardisation of reporting.

Anti-confound check: Is this general change resistance (confound) or knowledge-identity protection (BI)? The informant grounds the behaviour in knowledge-specific rationale (“seasonal adjustment factors built up over fifteen years”) rather than in opposition to the acquiring firm per se. The parallel system preserves domain-specific embedded knowledge, not organisational autonomy in general. Code retained as BI. Evidence type: Section B (process). Temporal marker: month 4. Hierarchical level: middle management.

Rule R4 check (process independence): This code is grounded in Section B process evidence (specific behaviour at month 4), independent of Section C outcome evidence (integration level). Rule R4 satisfied: inference is not circular.

Appendix C. Audit Trail Template

Note. The audit trail template below documents the analytical decisions made at each protocol stage for a single case. Researchers should complete one record per case. The completed records constitute the audit trail that enables external evaluation of analytical trustworthiness (Lincoln & Guba, 1985). This template is a ready-to-use instrument; adapt field labels to your domain.

Case Audit Record

Case identifier: _____ | Date of analysis: _____ | Analyst: _____ | Second coder (if applicable): _____

Stage 1 (Resolution): Record the number of data segments assigned to each layer (structural conditions / organisational responses / outcomes) and note any ambiguous assignments and their resolution.

Stage 2 (Redescription): Record the number of coded instances per construct (VK, UK, BI, PRO); document all anti-confound decisions made during coding; note inter-coder disagreements and their resolution; record Cohen’s kappa if applicable.

Stage 3 (Retrodiction): Record P2 probe responses by hierarchical level; document the reconstructed temporal sequence; note any discrepancies across informant levels and their resolution.

Stage 4 (Retroduction): Record the mechanism hypothesis as a formal proposition (MH-[case identifier]); note the specific process evidence from Stage 3 that grounds each hypothesis element; confirm that the hypothesis is grounded in Section B evidence independently of Section C (Rule R4).

Stage 5 (Elimination): List each rival explanation considered; document the specific evidence used to eliminate each rival; record the Rule R2 counterfactual test applied to each rival; note rivals retained as contextual moderators.

Stage 6 (Identification): Record the mechanism profile assigned (Table 4 Profile 1–5); document the discriminating evidence justifying the assignment; confirm Rule R5 (cross-level triangulation) is satisfied; note cases where profile assignment was ambiguous.

Stage 7 (Correction): If this case does not fit the assigned profile: document the nature of the discrepancy; record the revised mechanism hypothesis incorporating the boundary condition; document what the correction adds to the theoretical framework that was unavailable before the negative case was analysed.